

D3.2 Concrete recommendations for EUTOPIA institutional policies regarding Open Science*

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Executive summary

EUTOPIA Task 3.3 aims to stimulate and reward Open Science practices and contributions to multi-disciplinary problems that have real-life impact. This is done through active knowledge exchange on research assessment practice reforms across all EUTOPIA institutions. The actions under this task focused on formulating an EUTOPIA Framework Policy on Research Assessment. The entire process involved collecting input from various groups, such as the Vice-Rectors and HR-directors, and through workshops held at EUTOPIA institutions. These inputs were taken into account to formulate a Framework Policy, consisting out of five main sections: “Purpose of the document”, “Vision of EUTOPIA”, “General principles”, “Practical implementation” and “Indicator toolbox”. The “Vision of EUTOPIA”-section outlines why the EUTOPIA Alliance sees the need for research assessment reform. Subsequently, general principles are described along the lines of which the research evaluation system should be reformed. Next, the Framework Policy describes support actions that should be taken by institutions to support implementation of reforms. Lastly, a toolbox helps institutions to define appropriate indicators for reach level of evaluation that reforms could have an impact on. The impacts of the Framework Policy include knowledge exchange, creating greater alignment in research evaluation practices between EUTOPIA Universities and facilitating the development of implementation plans. Finally, discussions around the earlier versions of the Framework Policy also led to EUTOPIA signing the CoARA Agreement.

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1. Introduction

EUTOPIA-TRAIN Task 3.3 of WP3 aimed to create the framework conditions for Open Science practices to be incentivised and rewarded through research evaluation systems at EUTOPIA Universities. This task did not take place in isolation from other initiatives, as research assessment reform is central to the current European Research Area plans. The EUTOPIA Alliance is committed to enact these changes on the role of Open Science in research assessment at its universities.

The specific expectations were spelled out in the task description of the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project (Box 1). The expectations include a think-tank action, a Framework Policy and an implementation plan. This Deliverable reports how these actions were undertaken and what the main results are of Task 3.3. The expected impact of these deliverables is greater knowledge exchange in terms of research assessment practices, greater coherence on ongoing open science reforms, and the enhanced uptake of OS research assessment practices at EUTOPIA institutions.

Box 1. Objectives of WP3.3

[...] The overall goal of this task is to stimulate and reward Open Science practices and contributions to multi-disciplinary problems that have a real life rather than a pure academic impact. We will focus on the practical implementation of new metrics, where UL has previous experience in developing research performance indicators for the Guild network. The following steps will be taken to achieve this goal:

- Start-up a think-tank to address, amongst others, the following questions and concerns:
- How to measure/assess effective impact in the real world of Open contributions. Stimulating open contributions with a real-life impact will boost the progression of sustainable challenges
- How to implement assessment of Openness and FAIRness in research output (publications, archiving) and research process (Citizen Science, integrity, collaboration)
- How to create support for a research assessment reform
- Practical details of research assessment implementation such as the format of CVs and assessment templates, and incentives
- Design framework policies for research assessment which reflect Open Science practices and adopt a timetable for implementation
- Meeting notes, policy guidelines and other documents resulting from these discussions will be made available to the EUTOPIA community in order to create more transparency with regards to research career assessments (with WP4.3).
- Reach out to funders to involve them in the discussion (with WP1.5) [...]

The next sections include the background on research evaluation reform, which was the basis for developing the Framework Policy (Chapter 2). We also describe the process of formulating the Framework Policy (Chapter 3). The Framework Policy for Research Assessment itself is described in detail (Chapter 4). Lastly, the outlook, potential future developments and anticipated impacts of the Framework Policy are outlined (Chapter 5).

2. Context

2.1. Assessment reform as an EU policy priority

Reforming research assessment and advancing Open Science are two interlinked policy priorities of the European Union. They are included in the [reform agenda for the European Research Area](#) and received specific attention through the [2022 Council conclusions on Open Science and research assessment](#). University alliances play a special role in this reform agenda. According to the [2021 Council conclusions on the European Universities initiative](#), alliances are “*testbeds for innovative teaching and for research, including academic career assessment and rewarding systems that take into account inter alia open science practices, quality of teaching, transfer of knowledge and outreach*”.

The recently formed [Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment \(CoARA\)](#) has the purpose to create critical mass which overcomes the collective action problem (i.e., early movement disadvantaged the mover). It is based on the [Agreement on Reforming Research Assessment](#) (2022) that was developed by more than 350 institutions in Europe and beyond. This push does not limit itself to changes related to Open Science. Instead, research assessment should be seen in a larger context of making procedures, methods and sources more transparent and fair. The reforms on Open Science practices primarily relate to expanding the range of academic and research activities and outputs that should be considered in assessments at different levels.

2.2. EUTOPIA context and considerations

EUTOPIA is a diverse alliance with ten member universities whose long-term vision is “*to make a global impact on real-world challenges by empowering the new generations with academic knowledge.*”¹ From the start with the [EUTOPIA2050 project](#), Open Science has been one of the priorities of EUTOPIA. The work on Open Science has been included within the [EUTOPIA-TRAIN project](#) and will be continued through the [EUTOPIA-MORE action](#). The EUTOPIA Alliance like many other European Universities networks, seeks to foster different types of impact and academic activities, including in the area of Open Science. Examples are the goal to “*to promote innovation and societal impact*” or to “*open up their [the universities’] research structures for society, students and policymakers*” ([EUTOPIA-TRAIN](#)). The vision includes making them “*attentive to the plurality, potentiality and pre-eminence of Europe’s regions*” and to create “*powerful place-making partnerships*” ([EUTOPIA2050](#)). Elements of the [Values Statement](#) reflects this thinking, such as the focus on local environments, a culture of inclusion and diversity.

Within the EUTOPIA2050 project, a first foundation for the alignment of assessment and reward policies has been the adoption of the EUTOPIA Model Open Science Policy in mid-2022. This policy template (see Box 2) invites each EUTOPIA member to develop institutional frameworks and reward mechanisms which incentivise “*research quality and Open Science*”. It also refers to committing to previous declarations, such as the [San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment \(DORA\)](#). The

¹ <https://eutopia-university.eu/english-version/about-us/about-us-1>

model policy is an expression of intent for EUTOPIA research institutions to move towards assessment and reward systems which address Open Science. While the model policy spells out this shared ambition and commits EUTOPIA Universities to it, this Deliverable within EUTOPIA-TRAIN represents the operationalisation of the objective through the Framework Policy (including the Toolbox).

Box 2. EUTOPIA Open Science Policy

[...] **Research Assessment and Evaluation**

[Name of EUTOPIA institution] commits to:

1. Developing in cooperation with the other EUTOPIA institutions, funding agencies and institutional departments and other appropriate units a framework for research assessment and evaluation that incentivizes research quality and Open Science behaviors and practices following European developments on the topic and the work of the European Open Science Policy Platform. Such systems should take into consideration disciplinary differences and their impact on researchers at different career stages.
2. Setting up reward mechanisms for researchers using Open Science practices (e.g., sharing provisional results through open platforms, using open software and other tools, participation in open collaborative projects (citizen science) etc.)
3. Sign the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA) or another analogous declaration. [...]

3. Development of the Framework Policy

3.1. Conceptual approach and planning

Developing a Framework Policy which, on the one hand, is specific enough to drive changes of institutional practices while, on the other hand, respecting institutional autonomy and diversity is far from trivial. The first step was, therefore, reflecting on the objectives of the task and operationalising the entire process to formulate the Framework Policy. For this process, we consulted the [SCOPE Framework for Research Evaluation](#) that was developed by the INORMS Research Evaluation Group. The SCOPE Framework recommends five steps to follow when discussing or reforming evaluation and assessment issues. These are:

1. START with what you value
2. CONTEXT considerations
3. OPTIONS for measuring
4. PROBE deeply
5. EVALUATE your evaluation

When applied to the EUTOPIA Alliance, this led us to start with reflecting on the purpose of research assessment within the context of EUTOPIA. This phase also aimed to create awareness and support across the different stakeholder groups, and to align the activity with other relevant tasks within EUTOPIA-TRAIN (e.g., HR, Innovation...). We subsequently defined different activities following the five steps of SCOPE (See Table 1). This planning defined the scope and logic of the outputs of Task 3.3 of WP3. The last step of the SCOPE Framework (“EVALUATE”) was not addressed in this task because the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project only included the design of a Framework Policy but not the implementation at EUTOPIA institutions. The Framework Policy will be translated into

implementation roadmaps by each partner, which explain how a partner aims to implement the Framework Policy within their local context. The evaluation of the Framework Policy and executing the implementation plans at each EUTOPIA institution is included in the EUTOPIA-MORE project (see Section 5). Within EUTOPIA-TRAIN, there will be a template that is made to see what elements will be taken up in partner institutions' implementation plans.

Table 1. *Phased approach used within Task 3.3*

	Phase 1: START/CONTEXT	Phase 2: OPTION/PROBE	Phase 3: OPTION/PROBE
What	Think tank phase, reflection & preparatory phase	Framework design phase – translating the vision into something more practical	Practical recommendations phase
Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Desk research ▪ Discussion with other EUTOPIA WPs ▪ Local discussions with stakeholders at institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Synthesis of assessment approaches/options/metrics suitable for EUTOPIA vision ▪ Discussion with other EUTOPIA WPs ▪ Local discussions with stakeholders at institutions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Each partner develops an implementation plan based on the Framework Policy ▪ Brief toolbox as part of Framework Policy
Main outputs	Background notes, initial draft of principles	Framework Policy (Section 4 of this Deliverable)	None (to be finished in EUTOPIA-MORE)

3.2. Development process

As outlined above, the development process for the Deliverable was designed from beginning to be *iterative and interactive* and to allow *bottom-up input and exchanges with other EUTOPIA activities*. The process paid attention to involve different audiences within workshops and consultations (e.g., administrative staff, managers, professors, early-career researchers and doctoral candidates). Multiple groups of stakeholders were invited to provide specific feedback. Researchers and research support staff were invited to the institutional workshops, and EUTOPIA-TRAIN workshops. Presenters from the European University Association/Open University of Catalunya and Science Europe/Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment provided insights during the January 2022 and October 2022 workshops respectively. The Vice-Rectors for Research (25th of April) and the group of HR directors (26th of April) provided input on the Framework Policy. The bottom-up input of both researchers and support staff, and HR-directors and Vice-Rectors were important to ensure that the Framework Policy is aligned and coordinated across the alliance. This concerns in particular the EUTOPIA Research and Innovation Strategies and the human resources strategy, which are being developed by the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project in WP1, WP2, and WP4, respectively.

An overview of each major step that was undertaken is shown in Figure 1. First, desk research and brainstorming led to the initial plan for the Framework Policy. Deskwork also led to creation of Background note #1, which served as input for the cross-WP ideation workshop that was held. Afterwards, an initial draft of principles was created, which was circulated to EUTOPIA institutions. Some EUTOPIA institutions held internal workshops to provide specific feedback on these draft principles, while others held workshops discussing also the CoARA Agreement. A second background note was drafted after more in-depth desk research. Subsequently, the first draft of the Framework Policy and this Deliverable were composed. Next, this draft received feedback from all partners in

WP3. The Framework Policy subsequently was critically revised by the Vice-Rectors of Research of EUTOPIA institutions. This also included the 4 Vice-Rectors of the novel EUTOPIA members (*Babeş-Bolyai University, Technische Universität Dresden, The NOVA University Lisbon and Ca' Foscari University of Venice*) who were involved due to the continuation of open science reforms in EUTOPIA-MORE. This step was deemed essential to create broad-ranging support for the Framework Policy going into EUTOPIA-MORE. The Framework Policy therefore included broad solicitation across multiple partners and stakeholders. Lastly, the Framework Policy was reviewed internally and submitted as part of this Deliverable.

Figure 1. Development process of the Framework Policy (white=EUTOPIA-TRAIN; orange=EUTOPIA-MORE)

In this process, the following workshops were held:

- Cross-WP ideation workshop: “Research assessment and Open Science: Towards a Framework Policy for EUTOPIA” (EUTOPIA-wide, online) on 18th of January 2022 (See workshop agenda in Annex I)
- EUTOPIA Week in Brussel: “Moving Open Science Forward. Workshop for OS staff, grant officers (including GLENN), R&I staff, researchers” on 28th of June 2022.
- Vrije Universiteit Brussel Institutional Workshop: “A EUTOPIA framework for Open Science in research assessment” on 25 October 2022 (See workshop agenda in Annex I)
- University of Ljubljana Institutional Workshop : on 12 December 2022 (See workshop report in Annex I)
- Other research institutions held workshops that focused also signing the CoARA Agreement rather than the Framework Policy specifically.

As mentioned, during the process, two background notes were also written as part of EUTOPIA-TRAIN WP3 as a supportive measure during the phases 1 and 2 of our work. They investigate and explain the motivation for research assessment reform and helped identify and reflect upon different approaches for research assessment. Both documents have been released on Zenodo (see Box 3).

The first background note, entitled *“From impact factor to responsible evaluation. Overview of developments in research assessment and implications for EUTOPIA”* was released in early 2022 and formed basis for the cross-WP workshop in January 2022 as well as the overall planning and conceptual approach of Task 3.3. It explains the political context in more detail, as well as the different criticisms associated with traditional metrics. It also presents different attempts at reforming research assessment and analysed the implications for EUTOPIA and potentially other alliances. The report itself was made available on Zenodo and downloaded 359 times as of 12 June 2023.

The second background note, named *“Open Science in research assessment. An overview of quantitative and qualitative approaches”* was published in late 2022 in order to support the further development of the Framework Policy and toolbox. It collects approaches for measuring and evaluating Open Science practices ranging from quantitative to qualitative measures. This work was crucial to lay the foundations for the toolbox of practices and methods introduced at the end of the Framework Policy (Section 4 of this Deliverable). The report itself was made available on Zenodo and downloaded 329 times as of 12 June 2023.

Box 3. Background notes

Stoy, Lennart, & Maes, Elisa. (2022). *From impact factor to responsible evaluation. Overview of developments in research assessment and implications for EUTOPIA*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6323213>

EUTOPIA-TRAIN. (2022). *Open Science in research assessment. An overview of quantitative and qualitative approaches*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7097264>

4. EUTOPIA University Alliance Framework Policy on Research Assessment

Purpose of the Framework Policy

The **EUTOPIA University Alliance Framework Policy** describes the perspectives of the EUTOPIA University Alliance on how research evaluation practices could be reformed to stimulate open science practices. We envision that greater adoption of open science practices will ultimately lead to higher impact, efficiency and degree of reproducibility of research. The document is congruent with prior policy documents on research evaluation and open science, such as the *San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment*, *The Metric Tide*, *Leiden Manifesto* and *Indicator Frameworks for Fostering Open Science Knowledge Practices in Science and Scholarship*. In particular, the document draws on several elements covered within the recent *Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (CoARA) Agreement*. The CoARA Agreement has been signed by the EUTOPIA University Alliance.

The **EUTOPIA University Alliance Framework Policy** is divided into three main sections: (1) General principles; (2) Practical implementation; and (3) Toolbox of indicators. The “*General principles*” section described the open science practices, outputs and activities that the EUTOPIA University Alliance values. Furthermore, this section also outlines principles that guide the appropriate design and use of quantitative indicators. The “*Practical implementation*” section describes those commitments that EUTOPIA Universities should make to proactively support the local implementation of research evaluation reforms. The “*Toolbox of indicators*” section provides examples of approaches and indicators that may be used for each level of assessment. This overview is only indicative and does not contain an exhaustive exploration of potential indicators. EUTOPIA Universities can draw inspiration from this toolbox when they are designing indicators to fit the local context they operate in.

The **EUTOPIA University Alliance Framework Policy** will serve as the reference document for *implementation roadmaps* that will be developed by EUTOPIA Universities. These implementation roadmaps outline the plans for reforming local research evaluation procedures. The Framework Policy provides the common view and principles that all EUTOPIA Universities can base themselves on for drawing up their implementation plans. In this process, each University maintains full autonomy to decide what goals they will work towards in terms of research assessment reform, what elements they prioritize, how they will work towards these goals and at what speed. We expect that this will result in greater alignment in terms of research evaluation practices on open science practices across EUTOPIA Universities.

Vision of the EUTOPIA University Alliance

Academic research has many different goals, including contributing meaningfully to societal progress, public well-being and knowledge production. However, a plethora of policy documents has suggested that contemporary research evaluation practices do not adequately support these goals. The use of quantitative indicators in research evaluation processes are influencing competitive dynamics between individual researchers, research groups and institutions. Currently, those metrics most often employed do not adequately capture the multidimensionality of **scientific research processes, outputs, and impacts**. While they may incentivize some useful scientific activities, their unidimensional focus may cause researchers to neglect other – also scientifically valuable – activities. Researchers may prefer to dedicate their scarce time to well-rewarded activities rather than those that involve “invisible labour”.

If research evaluation gives disproportionate weight to output indicators, such as the number of publications, researchers may feel pressured to let number and speed take priority over quality and due process. This encourages *fast science* that ultimately comes at the cost of reproducibility of research results. Another concerning issue is that research impact is rather narrowly conceived. Citation-based metrics already capture impact in terms of the integration of publications into the academic work of others. However, the social, economic, political, technological and educational impacts of academic research are not always sufficiently taken into account. Lastly, researchers may not be actively stimulated to invest sufficient resources into disclosing all intermediary outputs of research, such as data, software, code and algorithms. The opening up and reuse of these outputs would enhance the efficiency of public investments made into research as it reduces redundancy. Furthermore, the lack of transparency over outputs does not allow easy replication of results by peers. These inherent flaws of current research evaluation practices cause the impact and efficiency of scientific research overall to be *below their theoretical optimum*. From this perspective, research evaluation practices can be considered *suboptimal* in encouraging those research practices that deliver the greatest benefits for society.

These aforementioned flaws can be addressed by adjusting research evaluation practices as outlined in many policy documents on open science and research evaluation. These range from recognizing the value and impact of all outputs in research, to reducing the influence of quantitative output indicators to acknowledging the broader impact of research beyond citations. These adjustments are envisioned to increase efficiency as research outputs can be routinely explored and reused for various purposes. Furthermore, the opening up of research outputs and processes is anticipated to partly remediate irreproducibility of research results. Lastly, the transformative potential of academic research may also be enhanced by better capturing and rewarding social, economic, political, technological and educational impacts of research. In summary, the synergistic effects created through stimulating cooperative behaviour and strengthening the science-society interface are anticipated to enhance the return-on-investment and impact of academic research overall.

Although the vision that we are working towards is clear, there will be many obstacles and unresolved issues on the road towards reforming research evaluation processes. Quantitative indicators have traditionally been of major importance in resource allocation mechanisms. They are commonly used throughout many different levels of research evaluation. Research evaluation procedures are currently being criticized for their excessive reliance on these quantitative indicators. Furthermore, the indicators themselves have been criticized for their statistical shortcomings. From

the socio-technical perspective, the use of indicators can also have detrimental effects, such as evaluators neglecting qualitative judgement due to the apparent objectivity of quantitative indicators. We need reappraisal of qualitative assessment itself in which quantitative indicators have their proper place. This might include using evaluation approaches where quantitative indicators are used as instruments to facilitate qualitative assessment (i.e., metrics-informed qualitative peer-review). Stimulating open science practices can lead to enhanced reproducibility, efficiency and impact of research in general. For this reason, the development of novel indicators related to various open science practices is essential. These indicators may relate to impacts of research, research processes or intermediary outputs, such as data and code sharing. While open science indicators may assist the transition towards open science practices, their implementation could still have unwanted effects. In order to limit the occurrence of unwanted effects, it is of paramount importance that the effects of integrating indicators into research evaluation are monitored and periodically assessed.

General principles

In accordance with the past manifestos, declarations and policy documents on research evaluation and open science, the general principles that underpin the vision of the EUTOPIA University Alliance are the following:

- The evaluation of individual researchers, research groups, departments and faculties should not focus exclusively on scientific publications. Instead, it should aim to incorporate a broad range of **academic activities** and **outputs**. These may include:
 - Disseminating research results through different routes (including preprints, conference papers, edited volumes and monographs) and modes (such as Open Access and in various languages)
 - Making all research outputs, such as making data and software, Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) and “as open as possible”
 - Contributions to research infrastructures, such as data infrastructures, that advance open science at different levels and disciplines
 - Engaging in valorisation of research, such as through university spin-offs, public-private (or other academic—non-academic) collaborations
 - Participating in activities that enhance the transparency of research processes and publication pipelines, such as (semi-)open peer review
 - Partaking in efforts to strengthen overall reproducibility of research results, such as using preregistration, Registered Reports and “good research practices for conducting and reporting” (e.g., checklists)
- The evaluation of research proposals should not focus *exclusively* on scientific contents of the proposal or prior achievement of researchers. It should also consider taking into account **appropriate research processes/practices**. These may include:
 - Plans to make all research outputs FAIR and “as open as possible”
 - Plans to adopt practices that enhance the transparency of research processes, such as preregistration or use of Registered Reports

- Ability of research teams to recruit expertise to successfully complete the proposed projects (e.g., involvement of statisticians, data management or software specialists)
- Evaluation procedures at all levels should adopt **a broad understanding of impact**. Impact assessment cannot be restricted to prestige of the publication venue or citation impact. Instead, impact assessment should encompass social, technological, policy, economic and educational dimensions. These types of impacts may be particularly relevant when they directly relate to overarching missions of research fields. This may include:
 - Social innovation and research results that are directly responsive to communities' needs
 - Valorisation of research, such as through university spin-offs, public-private (or other academic—non-academic) collaborations
 - References to research outputs in policy guidelines or demonstrable influence on development of policy or legislation
 - Reuse of research outputs by non-academic actors
 - Reuse of research outputs by students for training purposes
 - Demonstrable medium or long-term impact, such as increased quality of services or qualitative life-years
- All evaluation procedures, particularly those of individual researchers, should be **sensitive to context, and the division of labour within and across research groups**. This means that:
 - Not everyone has to tick all boxes: Evaluated criteria should be used conscious of researchers' career stage, academic profile and aspirations in academia. We endorse the LERU recommendation that *"Broad criteria are meant to recognize a variety of profiles, not to push researchers even further into stress."* Ideally, the achievements of individual researchers should be understood in function of their particular profile.
 - Research missions of the field, the nature of knowledge-production within scientific disciplines, as well as the multi-, inter- and trans-disciplinary approaches to research should be accounted for within evaluation. For instance, the evaluation of medical researchers might be influenced by the overarching mission of their field (i.e., improving public health). Evaluation should account for nature of knowledge-production within research fields, such as how conceptual, inductive and deductive work relate to each other. Ideally, the achievements of individual researchers and teams should be understood in the context of the characteristics of their field and their roles within that field.
- Research assessment practices should optimally support the quality, efficiency and impact of research overall. For this reason, **all quantitative indicators should be designed and used responsibly by all stakeholders**. This holds for both traditional output indicators and novel open science indicators. Open science indicators may relate to openness, impact, transparency and proper procedures of research outputs and processes. These indicators may be instrumental in promoting the widespread adoption of open science practices, which in turn is expected to lead to increased quality, efficiency and impact. The principles that guide responsible design and use of indicators are as follows:

- Indicators should be implemented responsibly. Indicators should only be used in contexts for which they were explicitly designed. Indicators must be closely scrutinized before implementation to manage the risk of potential unwanted effects occurring. This includes discussing assessing their methodological flaws, their coverage, whether reliable and transparent information sources for their calculation are available, and potential downstream effects of their implementation. Indicators that are understood to create unwanted effects after their implementation must be removed or updated.
- Indicators should be used responsibly. This means that evaluators are sufficiently aware of their methodological flaws and limited scope of indicators and their propensity to passively influence individual judgement (i.e., anchoring effects). Evaluators should recognize that (some) indicators can only be appropriately interpreted within disciplines and that they that they cannot be used to make generalist statements across all disciplines. Caution must be taken that the use of quantitative indicators does not reinforce (the perception of) “quantitative tallying cultures” where achievements are always reduced to their measurable quantitative dimensions. Indicators may be used differently according to the level of evaluation. Indicators used at aggregate levels should not trickle down into individual evaluation. Evaluators should not use indirect proxies of the criteria under evaluation. Instead, the contents of the research should preferably be addressed.
- Criteria that are taken into account in research evaluation processes must be transparent. Open science dimensions and related indicators can only work as incentives if they are explicitly recognized to be taken into account. This requires making them transparent to those under evaluation.
- **The potential shortcomings of purely qualitative approaches in research evaluation should be recognized.** They could be too labour-intensive for both reviewers and applicants, introduce inappropriate subjective considerations and advantage those proficient at writing. Qualitative approaches should be designed to minimize the potential of bias and manipulation. **The implementation of any novel approach should always be evaluated in terms of costs and scalability and should be subject to potential reconsideration.**
- Researchers are simultaneously collaborators and competitors within the current and future academic ecosystem. There may be some degree of tension between open science practices and being competitive within systems of performance-based resource allocation. Open science practices may also to some extent conflict with valorisation efforts. **An appropriate balance should be found between “openness” and “closedness” when considering research outputs that may be valorised locally (e.g., through university spin-offs).** This may involve establishing field-dependent timelines after which research outputs may be made open.

Practical implementation

All EUTOPIA Universities maintain institutional autonomy in deciding what goals they will prioritize and work towards, how they work towards these goals and at what speed. The local implementation of research evaluation reforms can be expected to face some difficulties, such as cultural acceptance and lack of tools to adequately support research evaluation practices. For this reason, EUTOPIA Universities commit themselves to support implementation in accordance with the aforementioned principles:

- EUTOPIA Universities will aim to promote the highest standards of research integrity, professional conduct and methodological rigour within their institutions
- EUTOPIA Universities will aim to implement research evaluation reforms while being respectful of the academic freedom of researchers and institutional autonomy
- EUTOPIA Universities will promote research evaluation cultures that aim to capture the multidimensionality and diversity of research outputs, activities and impacts
- EUTOPIA Universities will ensure that research evaluation reforms at their institutions are sufficiently communicated to local research groups, departments and faculties
- EUTOPIA Universities will ensure that local research groups, departments and faculties are empowered to implement these novel research evaluation practices at their institutions
- EUTOPIA Universities will closely follow international developments in terms of indicator development to facilitate local implementation of research evaluation reforms
- EUTOPIA Universities will collaborate with other research institutions to facilitate local implementation of research evaluation reforms

Toolbox of indicators

This toolbox provides concrete examples of indicators related to certain open science dimensions. Our conceptualisation of “research evaluation” encompasses hiring and promotion of individual researchers, the evaluation and monitoring of research groups, and assessment of funding proposals submitted by researchers. Notably, this also includes performance-based funding distribution mechanisms (e.g., to allocate financial resources to research departments). For this reason, we have categorized the “levels of evaluation” into individual-level, group-level and project-level. The examples of indicators are separated according to these different levels of evaluation. The toolbox does *not* provide comprehensive information on what elements could and should be assessed. It is limited to open science activities and related indicators. The toolbox excludes research evaluation of research institutions and related indicators (e.g., international rankings, performance-based funding distribution to research institutions). The term “indicator” is used in the broad sense. It includes quantitative output, process and impact indicators. Furthermore, it covers fully qualitative indicators, such as narratives and descriptions about open science activities. Any potential qualitative-quantitative indicators are also considered, such as scoring FAIRness of datasets through qualitative assessment. It should be noted that some indicators are only relevant and appropriate within certain disciplines.

1. Individual-level:

This level of evaluation includes: *“Periodical evaluation and deciding on hiring, promotion and tenure of individual researchers”*. We believe the following indicators might be useful:

- Research publications
 - Availability of pre-prints, Author Accepted Manuscripts and Version of Record publications in repositories
- Research data
 - FAIR and open status
 - Reuse of research data, including citations of data publications and data objects in repositories
- Software
 - FAIR and, if possible, open status
 - Reuse of software, including citations of software publications and software objects
- Describing in-depth any other notable research outputs within narrative CVs (e.g., “List five of your outputs that have substantially contributed to scientific progress”)
- Social, economic, technological, policy and educational impact of research activities (through quantitative indicators, demonstrable impact in narratives)
- Number and quality of peer-reviews

2. Group-level:

This level of evaluation includes: *“Periodical evaluation of the performance of groups, including departments and research groups, in function of evaluation and potentially resource allocation purposes”*. We believe the following indicators might be useful:

- Research missions and focus, specialisation and long-term strategy
- Research publications
 - Availability of pre-prints, Author Accepted Manuscripts and version of Record publications in repositories

- Research data
 - FAIR and open status
- Software
 - FAIR and, if possible, open status
- Contributions to research outputs (through quantitative indicators)
- Societal, economical, technological, and policy impact of research activities (through quantitative indicators, demonstrable impact in narratives)

3. Project-level:

This level of evaluation includes: *“Evaluation of grant applications on calls for projects”*. We believe the following indicators might be useful:

- Plans to make pre-prints, Author Accepted Manuscripts and Version of Record publications published OA
- Plans to make research data FAIR and open
- Plans to use recognized discipline-specific or generalist data infrastructures
- Plans to make software FAIR and, if possible, open
- Plans to maximize social, economic, technological, policy and educational impact of research activities
- Plans to enhance reproducibility of results (other than FAIRness and potential openness of research outputs)

Sources

The San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment (DORA). 2012. Available from: <https://sfdora.org/read/>

The Metric Tide. 2015. Available from: <https://www.ukri.org/publications/review-of-metrics-in-research-assessment-and-management/>

Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifesto for Research Metrics. 2015. <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>

Indicator frameworks for fostering open knowledge practices in science and scholarship. 2019. Available from: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/b69944d4-01f3-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1>

The Hong Kong Principles for assessing researchers: Fostering Research Integrity. 2020. Available from: <https://journals.plos.org/plosbiology/article?id=10.1371/journal.pbio.3000737>

Open Science and its role in universities: a roadmap for cultural change. 2018. Available from: <https://www.leru.org/publications/open-science-and-its-role-in-universities-a-roadmap-for-cultural-change>

A Pathway towards Multidimensional Academic Careers: A LERU Framework for the Assessment of Researchers. 2022. Available from: <https://www.leru.org/publications/a-pathway-towards-multidimensional-academic-careers-a-leru-framework-for-the-assessment-of-researchers>

Evaluation of research careers fully acknowledging Open Science practices. 2017. Available from: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/47a3a330-c9cb-11e7-8e69-01aa75ed71a1/>

5. Impact and outlook

We envision that the Framework Policy outlined in this document will help partner institutions develop their own policies around open science activities, including altering reward systems to support open science practices. Furthermore, the Framework Policy encourages knowledge exchange between partners. Overall, the increased degree of alignment across partner institutions will also avoid resources being wasted on “singular” initiatives, which are subsequently not adopted across the wider academic community. The dissemination of this Deliverable and background notes via Zenodo could also inspire other University Alliances to take steps to alter research assessment practices. These background notes have already been downloaded 688 times as of 12 June 2023. Lastly, the work within EUTOPIA-TRAIN WP3 led to broader discussions on research assessment within the Alliance, which in turn resulted in Alliance signing the CoARA agreement as an entity. In this way, the Alliance is formalizing its commitment to Open Science and research assessment.

The submission of this Deliverable marks the end of activities around research assessment within the EUTOPIA-TRAIN project. The work on reforming research assessment will be continued through the EUTOPIA-MORE project, which started in December 2022 and runs until November 2026. Notably, a task force on research assessment will be convened by mid-2023. The purpose of this group of experts is to accompany EUTOPIA members in the implementation of the Framework Policy by pooling expertise and advice in this shared journey. The project timeline also includes a review of the Framework Policy and how it has influenced implementation plans by end of 2024. This will be an important milestone in reflecting about the impact of the present deliverable and to adjust direction where necessary.

Annex I – Workshop agendas

Research assessment and Open Science: Towards a Framework Policy for EUTOPIA

Online workshop organised by EUTOPIA-TRAIN

Tuesday, 18 January 2022 (13:00-15:30 CET)

33 participants in total

13:00-14:00 - Plenary		
13:00	Opening and welcome	Jean-Claude Burgelman, Professor of Open Science Policies and Practices, VUB; EUTOPIA Advisory Board
13:05	Introduction to the workshop	Lennart Stoy, EUTOPIA Open Science Project Leader, VUB
13:10 (15m + 10m Q&A)	Presentation: Background and Impact of the UOC DORA Working Group and Action Plan	Pastora Martinez Samper, Vice President for Globalization and Cooperation, Open University of Catalunya
13:35 (15m + 10m Q&A)	Presentation: Working on fair and transparent assessment with the Warwick Principles	Yvonne Budden, Head of Scholarly Communications, University of Warwick
14:00-14:10 – Break		
14:10-15:10 – Breakout groups		
14:10	Introduction to breakout groups	Lennart Stoy, Project Leader, VUB
14:15	Breakout session #1: Defining activities and outputs of research	
14:30	Breakout session #2: Reflection about quantitative and qualitative methods for evaluation	
14:50	Breakout session #3: (Dis)advantages of assessment methods and principles for responsible evaluation	
15:10-15:30 – Plenary		
15:10	Wrap-up discussion and closing	
15:30	<i>End of workshop</i>	

A EUTOPIA framework for Open Science in research assessment

25 October 2022, 10:15-12:00

VUB workshop (in person)

Agenda

- Welcome and tour de table (10 minutes)

Part 1 – European Coalition on Advancing Research Assessment

- Presentation of the agreement and Coara (Dr James Morris, Senior Policy Officer, ScienceEurope) (20 minutes)
- Q&A (10 minutes)

Part 2 – EUTOPIA-level activities

- EUTOPIA activities around reforming research assessment and the initial EUTOPIA principles (Lennart Stoy, Open Science Project Leader, VUB) (15 minutes)
- Guided discussion (40 minutes)
- Closing – opportunity for final comments (10 minutes)

DRAFT

Zadeva: Vabilo na pogovor o reformi vrednotenja raziskovalne dejavnosti

12 September 2022

UniiversitTask 3.3 Development of open metrics and impact assessment

Report on the discussion at the University of Ljubljana regarding changing research assessment

The hybrid event took place on 12 December 2022 and was attended by 107 participants (87 over Zoom and 20 in the Assembly Hall of the Rectorate of the University of Ljubljana). Among the participants was also staff from the Human Resources Office of the Rectorate.

When we started to organize the event two months ahead, the plan was to structure it according to the recommendations, prepared by WP3 Lead Lennart Stoy for local consultations within the EUTOPIA TRAIN Task 3.3, i.e., presentation of research assessment proto-principles and open discussion around the suggested questions.

In November 2022, the Senate of the University of Ljubljana adopted a resolution that the University will sign the Agreement on reforming research assessment. With this, the University has also joined the Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment (COARA).

Consequently, the hybrid event on changing research assessment was designed as a discussion of rector of the University of Ljubljana Prof Dr Gregor Majdič with interested teachers, researchers and support staff on the Agreement on reforming research assessment and relevant activities at the University. Rector firstly presented developments that have led to the Agreement and to COARA (DORA Declaration, Leiden Manifesto), and after that the Agreement's principles for overarching conditions, assessment criteria and processes, and the core commitments.

Participants have raised the following points which were commented by the rector:

- Ethics and integrity in research are crucial;
- How feasible is implementation of qualitative assessment at the University of Ljubljana, i.e., where will the University with 3,600 teachers and researchers get adequate number of qualitative reviewers and how much will this cost, also how will they assess research publications in Slovenian language;
- What will be the consequences of changing research assessment for early career researchers;
- Slovenian Quality Assurance Agency for Higher Education (NAKVIS) will need to collaborate and align with changes of research assessment;
- Will other types of research results also be assessed, like FAIR and open research data, research software;
- In some research topics transfer of research results into practical applications is very important, how will this be assessed;
- How will changed assessment work for theory of fine arts.

In March 2023, activities regarding changing research assessment at the University of Ljubljana are going on in three tracks:

- Preparing changes of Rules and Regulations for Doctoral Studies at the University of Ljubljana regarding assessment of eligible mentors of PhD students;
- Drafting assessment of research according to the new Scientific Research and Innovation Activities Act;

- Preparing changes of Criteria for Appointment to the Titles of University Teachers, Researchers and Associates at the University of Ljubljana.

EUTOPIA TRAIN Task 3.3 assessment proto-principles are therefore already being introduced in the legal framework of the University of Ljubljana.

EUTOPIA Week session “**Moving Open Science forward – workshop on a comprehensive approach for EUTOPIA**” on Tuesday, 28 June, from 13h to 15h CEST. Please find below the agenda of the workshop:

- Welcome and objectives (5')
- Overview: Status of Open Science in EUTOPIA (15')
- Discussion (10')
- Breakout groups
 - Round 1: Taking stock (25')
 - Round 2: Identify opportunities (25')
 - Round 3: Prioritize options (25')
- Conclusions (10')

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